

Revival of Idolatry in Igbo Land: Implications to Contemporary Christian Praxis

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Abstract

The Igbo people of South-Eastern Nigeria, predominantly Christians, have witnessed a resurgence of interest in traditional religious practices in recent times. However, the most worrisome aspect of this development is the deviation into some obnoxious cultural and religious practices synonymous with idolatry. This phenomenon has significant implications for contemporary Christian praxis, as many Igbo Christians are being drawn back to the hitherto abandoned ancestral traditions. Thus, raising vital questions about the nature of Christian identity, the role of culture in shaping faith, and the effectiveness of Christian mission in the region. Using histo-analytical and comparative methodologies and secondary sources of data collection, it was discovered that insecurity, quest for quick wealth and loss of faith in contemporary Christianity praxis, are responsible for this shift to ancestral tradition, namely, idolatry, in Igbo land. The work recommended that a return to a contextualized Christian theology, incarnation ministry and collaborative engagement with traditional leaders will go a long way in the reorientation of the people, and make for genuine revival and appropriation of Christian tenets in Igbo land. God hates idol worship in all its facets. Christian leaders in Igbo land should step up their responsibilities in ensuring that Igbo land is cleansed of every iota of idolatry.

Keywords: Idolatry, Igbo land, Christian praxis, Contextualized theology.

Introduction

Walking through the communities and towns of Igbo land, one is confronted with sights that bulges the mind. It is surprising to observe that, many river banks, grooves and special trees in Igbo communities, are seen to be decorated

with white and red cloths; while blood, bones and skulls of animals used for sacrifice litter everywhere around the trees, river banks and grooves. At these sites, people gather for one religious activities and rituals or the other. There is indeed a revival and renaissance of idol worship in the whole of Igbo land. This upsurge, has therefore, become a burning issue, a major concern to Christian faith, as majority of the people are Christians. It is a phenomenon that transcends religious sphere but also has socio-cultural dimension, as it is deeply rooted in the traditions and customs of the Igbo people.

The advent of Christianity in Igbo land during the colonial era led to a significant decline in traditional religious practices. Many Igbo people converted to Christianity and the faith became an integral part of Igbo culture and identity. However, as colonialism waned and post-colonialism sets in, there seems to have been a renewed interest in pre-colonial traditions and cultural practices that have since gone into oblivion (Nwala, 1985). This development has seriously challenged contemporary Igbo Christians; as many are now between and betwixt in matters of faith and practice, not knowing exactly how to balance Christianity and ancestral traditions (Uchendu, 2017).

According to Uchendu (1965), the resurgence of idolatry is a response to the perceived failure of Christianity and western values to address the socio-economic challenges faced by the Igbo people. The author argued that idolatry provides a sense of identity and belonging that is lacking in the modern and globalized world and its systems. In the same line of thought, Nwosu (2018), accentuated that the rise in idolatry is linked to the increasing disillusionment with the political and economic situation in Nigeria. It offers a form of escapism for the people, allowing them to retreat into a world where they feel empowered and in control.

On the other hand, Okafor (1992), arguing differently noted that, the resurgence of idolatry is not a rejection of Christianity or western values, but rather a reinterpretation of them. The Igbo people are not turning to idolatry because they are disillusioned but because they are seeking to reconcile their traditional beliefs with their Christian faith. This suggests that the upsurge of idolatry is not a regression, but a form of cultural evolution. The revival of idolatry in Igbo land is a complex issue that requires a nuanced understanding of the socio-cultural context. While there is no one-size-fits-all solution, it is clear that any effective response must take into account the unique challenges and aspirations of the Igbo people (Okafor, 1992).

It is true that scholars like Uchendu (1965), Nwala (1985), and Okafor (1992), have adumbrated the facts of the resurgence of idolatry in Igbo land, they did not however, underscore the reviving dimensions, quests and zeal at which this

resurgence is affecting contemporary Christian theology and practice in Igbo land. This is the gap this work seeks to fill. Therefore, this paper aims at exploring the factors responsible for the revival of idolatry in Igbo land, and how this interrogates the contemporary Christian faith and practices and the way forward. Using histo-analytical and sociological methods and secondary sources of data collection, it was discovered that many Igbos of all ages today, are between and betwixt in their religious conviction. One leg in Christianity and the other in idolatry. Thus questioning the place of Christian tenets that object to double standard in the worship of God. In the next sub-heading, the researchers will consider the concept of idolism in Igbo land.

Idolatry Conceptualized

Halbertal, Margalit & Goldblum (1992) said that idolatry as a concept, is the worship of an idol as though it were a deity. It connotes the worship of something or someone other than the Supreme Being or God (Leone, 2016). In monotheistic religions (Judaism, Christianity, Islam etc.), idolatry is considered the “worship of false gods” and is forbidden by texts such as the Ten Commandments (Doniger, 1999).

The history of idolism in Igbo land is complex and multi-dimensional. The Igbo people before the coming of the western missionaries, had a rich and diverse traditional religious system. They believed in a supreme God, ‘Chukwu’, who was considered to be the creator of the universe. However, ‘Chukwu’ was not directly worshipped and instead, the Igbo people focused on worshipping a pantheon of lesser gods and goddesses, known as “alusi” (Mbiti, 1969). Ikenga (1987), posited that God is conceived to be great, and cannot be reached directly, but is approached through divinities. Thus, in the structure of their belief the Igbos (Africans) do not see God as being of the same rank and file with the divinities and spirits. Nwala (1985), noted that in Igbo culture from history, idols are primarily understood as representation of various spirits or deities within their traditional belief system, known as *odinani*, where people would worship multiple deities like *Ala* (earth goddess), *Amadioha* (thunder god), and *Ekwensu* (trickster god), through symbolic effigies, seeking their favour through offerings and rituals. Thus the practice of idolism (idol worship) is seen by some as part of African religious structure and culture which is significant in African spirituality.

Theoretical Framework

Postcolonial theory of Bhabha (1994), is considered a suitable theoretical framework for this work. The theory offers a robust lens through which to

examine the revival of traditional practices leading to revival of idolatry and the how this impinges on Christian praxis in Igbo land today. Postcolonial theory emphasizes the agency of colonized peoples in reshaping their identities. This framework helps in understanding how colonial power dynamics have influenced religious practices and identities in the region (Isichei, 1995; Falola & Heaton, 2008), which includes how individuals and communities have reclaimed and redefined their religious practices. This perspective is crucial for understanding the dynamic and evolving nature of religious identity in the region and why one religion is being de-emphasized, while the other is emphasized (Kalu, 2008; Nwoye, 2011). A central concern of postcolonial theory is how colonized societies adapt and transform imposed cultural elements. This includes syncretism, where local traditions and foreign religious practices merge. Scholars like Homi Bhabha have discussed cultural hybridization, a process highly relevant to how Igbo traditional practices have blended with Christianity and how traditional practices have attracted much interests by a section of the people, thus leading to what is described as the revival of idolatry in Igbo land (Bhabha, 1994; Kalu, 2008).

Revival of Idolatry in Igbo Land: Reasons

There has been a growing trend among a section of the Igbo people to re-embrace and practice traditional religious beliefs, including the worship of ancestral deities and spirits, which is often associated with the use of idols and imagery representations. Okafor (1992), acknowledged this fact, by referring it to as a desire by the people to preserve their cultural heritage and identity. While agreeing with Okafor (1992), the paper further argue that the quest to 'return to the root' as often used by supporters of this practice, could be due to the declining influence of Christianity in the region; and or due to the potential misinterpretations or excesses in the practice. Today, many young Igbo people are actively seeking to reconnect with their traditional roots, leading to a renewed interest in Igbo deities, rituals, and art forms. It has become so worrisome, that this revival might lead to a literal interpretation of idol worship which could contradict the values of modern Igbo society, with predominant Christian adherents.

This upsurge of idolatry among Igbo people most especially, the young ones, is a significant socio-cultural issue that has been given attention in recent years. This phenomenon is not only a religious concern but also a socio-cultural one that affects the overall development of the Igbo people mostly the youths and the larger society (Nwosu, 2018). Many reasons have been adduced to as the cause for this revival.

The first cause of this upsurge can be traced to the erosion of traditional Igbo values and the influence of western culture (Eze, 2016). The Igbo society, like many other African societies, is undergoing rapid socio-cultural changes due to globalization. This has led to a decline in the adherence to traditional Igbo values and an increase in the acceptance of western values, which often conflict with the traditional Igbo worldview. This view is true to what is witnessed in Igbo land today. New values of quick wealth syndrome, lack of value for human life and dishonesty, lack of spirit of enterprise and industry, have replaced the core values of dignity of labour, respect to authority, among other moral values enshrined in African culture. This cultural shift has contributed to the rise in idolatry among people, mostly the youth.

Lack of proper religious education and guidance can be a contributing force. Many Igbo youths are not adequately educated about their traditional religious beliefs and practices, leading to misconceptions and misunderstanding (Nwosu, 2018). This lack of knowledge and understanding has made them susceptible to the allure of idolatry. Christian values are part of the core moral givens inculcated to children and adults Igbo land, as the region is predominantly dominated by Christianity. But unfortunately, misguided priorities have shifted the views of many in the clime.

On the other hand, the influence of peer pressure and the desire for social acceptance also play a significant role in the revival of idolatry among Igbo youths (Eze, 2016). In their quest for social acceptance and belonging, many Igbo youths are drawn into idolatrous practices. Eze (2016) was quite right in this submission. These young people are usually, carried away by material quest and flashy lifestyle seen among their peers. Thus leading to unhealthy competition and going to any length in order to acquire wealth, not minding the consequences.

Nwala (1985), noted that the resurgence of traditional beliefs can create tensions within the Igbo Christian community, as some may struggle to reconcile their faith with certain aspects of Igbo spirituality. It is indeed a complex issue that requires a nuanced understanding of the socio-cultural and religious context. Okafor (1992), rightly points out that the key lies in respecting the cultural heritage of the people, while also providing them with the tools to navigate the modern world.

Idolatry, Insecurity and the Rising Crime in Igbo Land

Idolatry and insecurity in Igbo land have been a point of intense discourse. Insecurity is a situation where people find it difficult to enjoy safety of lives and

property. Igbo land has witnessed insecurity of lives and properties, both in the rural communities and the cities (Eze, 2018).

Ejizu (1986), accentuated the rate of insecurity in Igbo land. It is a situation where kidnapping, human trafficking, political violence, inter communal wars, boundary disputes, armed robbery pose security challenges in Igbo land. The efforts of security agencies to stem the tide have usually, proved abortive. The researchers also noted that the quest for secession by various groups in Igbo land and the poor perceived poor handling of the situation by the government, also heightened insecurity in Igbo land. In order to safeguard themselves, the people have to devise any means available including traditional means, such as using charms and invocation of the gods of the land, leading to idolatry.

Kalu (1985), observed that traditional religious practices play pivotal role in the explanation, predication and control of space-time events that yield dividends of order, security and prosperity. It is so due to lack of faith and confidence in the tenets of Christian religion. These traditional practices help in explaining mysterious events, predicting the future and controlling socio-political, economic and religious events that are likely to bring disaster and insecurity.

Religion generally, has been described as a product of insecurity, fear and crisis of the primordial men. Traditional African religions, originated from the early man's feeling of insecurity in the midst of cosmic and supernatural powers that threaten his existence (Ejizu, 1986). The primitive man was emotional and cognitive of the events that were looked upon as mysterious and awesome (Akpan, 2011). Naturally, Africans engage in traditional practices to handle security issues where they arise, through divination, rituals, sacrifices and observance of taboos.

Furthermore, passing through some towns in Igbo land, like Onitsha, Aba, Okigwe, Umuahia, Enugu, Awka, Abakiliki and others, one discovers that the crime rate in these towns are at alarming stage. Some of these cities are notorious for robbery: pick-pocketing, car theft, hired killing, cheating, burglary and so on (Anugwom, 2011). Udeagha (1995), identified drug peddling and abuse as key factor in the rising insecurity and criminality in Igbo land. It was discovered that people pass through these towns carrying their hearts in their hand, for not knowing what will befall them. Especially, during night hours.

Another factor engineering increase in crime rate, is the activities of fake native doctors in Igbo land. They aid and abet criminality like kidnapping, robbery, ritual killing and all forms of murder in the region. They provide charms that embolden these criminals (Ezeh, 2013). Soludo (2023), decried the increase in criminal activities and idolatry in Anambra state. He argued that idolatry is on the rise in Igbo land and that there is a nexus between criminality, kidnapping

and idolatry in Igbo land. He noted that the charms given to the criminals by the native doctors make them have false confidence to be more daring. This statement of Soludo (2023), aligns with authors' views. Native doctors and priestesses, erect their shrines at every corner, grooves and rivers in Igbo land attending to their clients and thus re-igniting the quest for 'return to the root.' The prevalence of insecurity and rising crime in Igbo land have led many to resort to all forms of measures to secure their lives and property. They visit shrines, insert charms, carry protective armlets and beads, or rings, believed to have the potency to ward off harms from the enemies. Others have instituted these practices by setting up shrines, revering and placating what is considered sacred objects and trees, by all manner of sacrifices and ritual practices. All these are done with a view that since the government cannot protect the people adequately, they will not fold their hands and watch their enemies destroy them. This has really, drawn some criticisms. Viewed from any perspective, insecurity and the increase in crime rate breed idolatry in Igbo land and vice versa.

Idolatry, Materialism and the 'Okeite' Syndrome

The connection between idolatry, materialism and 'Okeite' syndrome in Igbo land, is intriguing. There is a prevailing unethical and deadly ritual activities among young Igbos in recent times, amidst the sudden rise of cultural revival in the society. Many young people now perceive traditional religious practices and beliefs as more effective in achieving success and prosperity than Christianity. This has led to diverse deadly rituals (both for quick wealth and power) among Igbo youths (Chukwudebelu, 2021). This scenario is characterized by an ongoing surge of Igbo youths congregating in places like Oba, situated in the Idemili North Local Government of Anambra State. These youths, seeking spiritual empowerment, engage in money-related rituals and participating in sacrifices under the umbrella of the "Okeite ritual." This ritual is orchestrated and facilitated by a young, indigenous healer named Chukwudozie Nwangwu who is commonly referred to as "Akwa Okuko Tiwaraki." On daily basis, Chukwudozie Nwangwu, interacts with a sizable crowd, estimated to be around 50 to 100 individuals, primarily comprising of youths (Chukwudebelu, 2021). Discussing the "Okeite ritual," Nnatuanya (2022), observed that, it is charm prepared with different animals, including dog, elephant, and monkeys and sometimes human parts may be involved. The preparation involves the use of different types of herbs, roots and other ritual materials with the combination of different kinds of drinks.

There are numerous reasons why the present youths have ventured into this 'Okeite' charm and ritual. Prominent among them are quest for quick wealth, laziness, lack of employment opportunities, lack of fear of God and promotion of idolatry in the name of cultural revival among many other factors. The recent rise of traditional religious practices is also a major factor responsible for such a deadly ritual among Igbo youth (Nnatuanya, 2022). Hence, in line with the above, it is becoming more obvious that the resurgence of traditional religious activities occasioned by many factors, is now presenting significant social challenges for both the Christian church and the Igbo community.

Idolatry and the Challenge to Christian Practice

The resurgent of indigenous beliefs and customs, particularly among the young people in Igbo land, is evident in the growing popularity of traditional religious groups. This trend signals a shift from Christianity and the questioning of its influence on the culture and religious practices. Christianity has been erroneously perceived as having eroded African traditional culture, values, and practices, leading to the need to seek for a reconnection with the cultural heritage of the people (Njoku, 2023).

The rise underscores the desire to reclaim traditional religious practices perceived as more aligned with the people's values and culture. To some, Christianity is viewed as a foreign imposition, prompting a rejection in favour of indigenous belief (Njoku 2023). This trend reflects a growing curiosity among the Igbos towards their ancestral religious practices and posing a significant challenge to the Christian faith in the region.

Scholars such as Ngangah (2020), supported this observation. He highlighted that the "uka odinani" (traditional worship) aims to revive and promote traditional Igbo religious practices. These practices include ancestor veneration, divination, and the performance of traditional ceremonies and rituals. This worship emphasizes the importance of traditional values like respect for elders, humanity, cohesion and environmental stewardship. These put together, have lend credence to the notion that the resurgence of indigenous beliefs among the Igbo youths is not merely a passing trend but a meaningful cultural and spiritual movement. Thus, challenging Christian faith in different dimensions:

1. **Decline in Church Attendance:** The revival of obnoxious traditional cultural practices (idolatry), poses a significant challenge to the dominance of Christianity in Igbo land, leading to a decline in church attendance and Christian identification. Nwadiolor and Nwokocha (2023) highlighted this trend, by noting that the growing cultural revival movement has contributed to the decreasing number of individuals attending church

services in the region. Anizoba and Aande (2021), further emphasized the negative implications of this cultural revival movement on the Christian church in Igbo society. As more individuals embrace traditional religious beliefs and customs, the influence of the Christian church has waned, resulting in a decline to church attendance and a decrease in the number of people identifying as Christians.

2. **Syncretism in Igbo Christianity:** Another challenge of idolatry in Christian practices is that it has led to the emergence of syncretism, which refers to a state of religious confusion and crisis where traditions of different religions are mixed and practiced arbitrarily and associated together to the extent of betraying Christian ideals (Okoro, 2018). This blending of traditions has led to a state of dual allegiance and syncretism among its adherents, creating a perplexing state of religious fusion (Ejizu, 2000). This has caused a loss of clear definitions of Christian faith and confusion about what it means to be a Christian, making it difficult to maintain the integrity of Christian beliefs and practices among many Igbo Christians and leading to confusion about the nature of doctrines and Christian faith. However, Ejizu (2000) posited that the assimilation of beliefs and practices that are not yet in harmony with Christian teachings like ancestor worship or divination, may result in the weakening or misrepresentation of Christian teachings and practices.
3. **Religious Intolerance and Conflict:** Another challenge of idolatry to Christian practices in Igbo land is that it has led to instances of religious intolerance, where adherents of these traditional beliefs discriminate against Christians, thus, creating a hostile environment for those who do not follow traditional customs (Nwadiolor and Nwokocho, 2023).

Remedy to Idol Worship in Igbo Land

There is every need to nip in the bud, the menace of idolatry in Igbo land; before it goes out of hand. The remedies to this revival of obnoxious traditional practices culminating into idol worship in Igbo land, demand a multidimensional approach that addresses holistically, the cultural, spiritual and socio-economic aspects of the issue. According to Nwala (1985), it is important to adopt a broader and effective measure that promotes religious tolerance, preserves cultural heritage, and fosters social cohesion, while finding solution to the matter under discourse. Thorough understanding of the youths, their motivations and concerns is required, as well as meaningful dialogue between religious leaders, community stakeholders, and government institutions.

It is eminently imperative to address the enabling factors such as unemployment and lack of opportunities, which are responsible to the vulnerability of youths to unethical practices and criminal engagements. The saying that “an idol mind, is the devil’s workshop,” is true in this instance. Eze (2019), noted that, investing in education, skill development and acquisition, and community empowerment programs, can help ameliorate these challenges and promote a sense of hope and belonging among the youth.

To counter the narrative of idolatry and violence associated with traditional religious practices, there is need to promoting a nuanced understanding of indigenous beliefs and customs that emphasize the cultural significance and positive aspects while rejecting obnoxious practices that violate ethical and moral principles (Eleweke, 2022). This will lead to what is described as contextualization or inculturation. That is, presenting the Gospel in a clearer and comprehensive terms and doing away with the cultural practices that are evil, while retaining the good ones. Idowu (1973) posited that though Africans have welcomed the missionaries and enlisted in the new religion, the message of Christ cannot be said to be fully assimilated, internalized and appropriated by these converts. The missionaries were convinced that they had a clear message but they imposed it on the people in a manner that totally disregarded their religious genius and in a language that was incomprehensible to them. Nwabuko (1998), noted that the Christian message which arrived in Africa, was highly encoded and only the foreign missionaries and their indigenous counterparts who have been properly schooled in ancient, medieval and modern western or European philosophy can interpret the codes. African Christians need to comprehend this encoded message in order to play along.

Furthermore, inculturation demands that the Gospel message, the curriculum for theological studies and pastoral training for church leaders, be drawn up with a heavy accent on the questions that are being asked by Africans. It demands that Seminarians and students of African religion be made first to properly understand the conceptual details and frameworks of both traditional and Christian religions, before engaging in dialogue (Edeh, 1985). This demands that an appropriate spirituality be developed by African Christians, which will take into cognizance the existential situation of the people in its entirety (Gehman, 1987).

Conclusion

The revival of idolatry in Igbo land poses significant challenges to the contemporary Christian praxis. A lot of factors are contributing to this reality, such as quick wealth syndrome, declining effective Christian messages and the

quest to reclaim lost cultural traditions. This is a critical issue that requires a thoughtful and meaningful response from Christian leaders and practitioners, as it has great implications for Christian witness and ministry in the region. Adopting a comprehensive and contextualized approach, Christian leaders can effectively respond to the revival of idolatry in Igbo land, by promoting a vibrant and transformative Christian praxis that is all encompassing.

Recommendations

The following recommendations have been adduced based on the research carried out:

1. That Christian leaders and practitioners be culturally sensitive and aware, avoiding simplistic or judgmental approaches to matter relating to idolatry in Igbo land
2. Christian leaders should endeavour to re-examine their approaches to evangelism and discipleship, taking into consideration the cultural and historical context of the Igbo people. Also to dialogue and collaborate with traditional leaders and practitioners, seeking to understand their perspectives and find a common ground.
3. The Leadership of Christian groups in the region should prioritize theological education and training, equipping themselves to address the complexities of idolatry and promote a nuanced Christian response.
4. The Churches in Igbo land should engage in prayer and spiritual warfare, recognizing the spiritual dimensions of idolatry and seeking God's guidance and empowerment in the eradication of the practice.

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